

A Systematic Study of Physics-Informed Neural Networks for the Level-Set Interface Advection

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We present a systematic ablation study of physics-informed neural networks (PINNs) for level-set advection across four benchmarks of increasing complexity: linear translation (TR), solid-body rotation (RO), reversed vortex deformation (RV), and the Zalesak rotating slotted disc (ZD), covering 58 experiments. For TR, a step learning rate scheduler (StepLR) with eikonal weight $w_{\text{eik}} = 1.0$ is optimal (mean L^2 error $\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{L^2} = 2.09 \times 10^{-4}$). For RO, cosine annealing (CosineAnnealing, minimum learning rate $\eta_{\text{min}} = 10^{-5}$) outperforms StepLR, establishing that scheduler choice is benchmark-specific and cannot be transferred. For RV, reducing w_{eik} from 1.0 to 10^{-4} yields an $82\times$ improvement ($\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{L^2} = 1.51 \times 10^{-3}$, mean relative L^2 error $\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{L^2}^{\text{rel}} = 0.43\%$, final time $T = 2$); extending to $T = 8$ with causal weighting and residual-based adaptive distribution and refinement (RAD+RAR) achieves 0.63%, outperforming the PirateNet state-of-the-art (Sota) of Mullins *et al.* (2025) (0.85%) using a standard tanh network. For ZD, four studies address eikonal tuning (S1), trajectory-aware collocation (S2), architecture and causal weighting (S3), and adaptive sampling (S4). Random Fourier feature (RFF) encoding (bandwidth $\sigma = 2$) with $w_{\text{eik}} = 10^{-2}$ and causal weighting achieves $\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{L^2} = 5.74 \times 10^{-4}$ ($10\times$ reduction over the tanh baseline, S3); adding RAD+RAR with RFF $\sigma = 5$ and $M = 32$ causal chunks achieves the best overall ZD result: $\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{L^2} = 4.64 \times 10^{-4}$ ($\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{L^2}^{\text{rel}} = 0.13\%$) in 15.2 min (S4), outperforming the published Sota. A key finding is an RFF–eikonal joint design constraint: at low bandwidth ($\sigma = 2$), weak eikonal regularization ($w_{\text{eik}} = 10^{-4}$) distorts the signed-distance field and underperforms the tanh baseline, whereas higher bandwidth ($\sigma = 5$) is compatible with moderate regularization ($w_{\text{eik}} = 10^{-3}$) and yields the global best result. This bandwidth-dependent constraint has not been identified in the PINN literature.

Keywords: physics-informed neural networks, level-set advection, Zalesak benchmark, Random Fourier Features, eikonal regularisation, causal training, interface capturing.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Accurate tracking of moving phase boundaries is central to the numerical simulation of immiscible, incompressible two-phase flows encountered in free-surface hydraulics, gas–liquid pipelines, bubble columns, and droplet dynamics¹. In such flows the interface separating the two phases must be evolved under the local velocity field while preserving geometric fidelity and phase-volume conservation. Numerical errors in the interface transport step, such as loss of thin geometric features, artificial smoothing of sharp gradients, and drift of the enclosed phase volume, propagate directly into the coupled flow solution, making interface accuracy a prerequisite for predictive multiphase simulations.

The level-set (LS) method² is one of the most widely used Eulerian interface-capturing techniques in computational multiphase flow. By representing a moving phase boundary as the zero contour of a smooth scalar field, the method provides a convenient framework for computing interface normals and curvature directly from the field gradients, and handles topological changes such as merging and breakup without special treatment. Together with the Volume-of-Fluid (VoF) approach³, it forms the backbone of modern Eulerian front-capturing methodology. The principal weakness of the LS method, however, is the absence of strict mass conservation: numerical diffusion gradually distorts the level-set field, causing the enclosed phase volume to drift over extended integration times⁴. Reinitialization procedures restore the signed-distance property but introduce additional algorithmic parameters and can themselves perturb the interface position. Mass-conserving hybrid formulations that couple the level-set field with a supplementary transport mechanism alleviate the conservation problem^{1,5}, yet at the cost of increased implementation complexity. These persistent difficulties have motivated the exploration of mesh-free, data-driven alternatives that might sidestep explicit reinitialization and grid-dependent diffusion altogether.

Physics-informed neural networks (PINNs)⁶ are one such alternative. A PINN approximates the solution field by a neural network whose parameters are optimized to satisfy the governing partial differential equation (PDE) through a residual-based loss evaluated via automatic differentiation, requiring neither a mesh nor labeled training data. PINNs have been applied successfully to a broad class of forward and inverse problems, but their use in convection-dominated and long-time hyperbolic settings remains challenging. Two failure modes are particularly relevant to level-set advection. First, standard fully-connected

networks suffer from spectral bias⁷: they learn low-frequency solution components preferentially and struggle to resolve thin geometric features such as interface boundaries. Second, when the PDE residual is enforced globally over the full time horizon, the optimizer can satisfy the loss at later times without having learned the solution correctly at earlier times, a temporal propagation failure analyzed in detail by⁸ and⁹. Random Fourier Feature (RFF) input encodings address the first issue by expanding the representable frequency bandwidth of the network¹⁰, while causality-aware loss weighting tackles the second by imposing a sequential temporal structure on the training objective¹¹.

A small but growing body of work applies PINNs to interface and two-phase flow problems. Qiu et al.¹² used a PINN-based phase-field formulation for two-phase flows, and Buhendwa et al.¹³ demonstrated that velocity and pressure fields can be inferred from scattered interface-position data in incompressible two-phase settings. Most directly relevant to the present study, Mullins et al.¹⁴ applied the PirateNet architecture¹⁵, which combines Fourier feature embeddings, random weight factorization, and sequence-to-sequence (seq2seq) causal training, to level-set advection benchmarks including the Zalesak slotted disc and a time-reversed vortex deformation flow, reporting state-of-the-art (Sota) relative L^2 errors of 0.14% and 0.85%, respectively. Their study convincingly shows that an advanced PINN architecture can solve level-set problems without upwind stabilization or reinitialization. What it does not address, however, is how the individual ingredients (learning-rate schedule, eikonal regularization strength, collocation sampling strategy, and input encoding) interact in the level-set context, or which of these choices matter most as the interface geometry changes from smooth circles to slotted discs.

The present work fills this gap through a systematic ablation study of PINNs for level-set advection across four benchmarks of increasing geometric complexity: linear translation (TR), solid-body rotation (RO), reversed vortex deformation (RV), and the Zalesak rotating slotted disc (ZD). The objective is to isolate and rank the individual design decisions so that practical guidelines can be drawn for PINN configuration in interface advection problems. Specifically, we examine: (i) learning-rate scheduling strategies and their benchmark sensitivity; (ii) the role of eikonal signed-distance regularization as the single most influential loss hyperparameter; (iii) importance-weighted collocation sampling that targets geometrically localized features such as the Zalesak slot; and (iv) RFF input encoding combined with causal temporal weighting, together with the constraints this pairing imposes on the regularization strength.

The main contributions are as follows. (i) We provide complete benchmark-by-benchmark ablation tables covering 58 experiments, enabling full reproducibility. (ii) We show that the optimal learning-rate schedule is benchmark-dependent (step learning rate scheduler, StepLR, for TR; cosine annealing, CosineAnnealing, for RO; and setting-dependent for RV, where StepLR suffices at $T = 2$ but CosineAnnealing is required at $T = 8$) and must therefore be treated as a primary tuning dimension rather than a fixed implementation choice. (iii) We demonstrate quantitatively that the eikonal weight is the dominant hyperparameter governing accuracy, with the optimal value shifting from $w_{\text{eik}} = 1.0$ for rigid-body problems to $w_{\text{eik}} = 10^{-4}$ under severe interface deformation (an $82\times$ error reduction on RV). (iv) We identify a bandwidth-dependent RFF–eikonal joint design constraint: at low bandwidth ($\sigma = 2$), weak eikonal weight ($w_{\text{eik}} = 10^{-4}$) distorts the signed-distance field and underperforms a plain tanh baseline; at higher bandwidth ($\sigma = 5$), moderate regularization ($w_{\text{eik}} = 10^{-3}$) suffices and yields the global best ZD result. This constraint has not been reported previously. (v) For the Zalesak benchmark we provide a four-study programme (S1–S4) that separates the contributions of eikonal tuning, trajectory-aware sampling, architecture plus causal weighting, and adaptive collocation refinement. Study S4 demonstrates that RFF $\sigma = 5$ combined with RAD+RAR and $M = 32$ causal chunks achieves the best result across all ZD experiments ($\overline{\mathcal{E}}_{L^2}^{\text{rel}} = 0.13\%$, $\overline{\mathcal{E}}_{L^2} = 4.64 \times 10^{-4}$), while training in only 15.2 min on a single graphics processing unit (GPU).

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section II briefly reviews the level-set method. Section III presents the benchmark definitions, PINN formulation, training protocol, and error metrics. Sections IV and V report results for the smooth-interface benchmarks and the Zalesak benchmark, respectively. Section VI discusses design principles and limitations, and Section VII concludes the paper.

II. THE LEVEL-SET METHOD

A. General level-set formulation

In the level-set framework², a moving interface $\Gamma(t)$ is represented implicitly as the zero contour of a scalar field $\phi(\mathbf{x}, t)$ defined on a fixed spatial domain $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^2$. The interface location is given by $\Gamma(t) = \{\mathbf{x} \in \Omega : \phi(\mathbf{x}, t) = 0\}$, and the sign of ϕ distinguishes the two phases. In this work we consider pure kinematic interface advection under a prescribed velocity field $\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ and take $\Omega = [0, 1]^2$.

The evolution of ϕ is governed by the level-set advection equation:

$$\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial t} + \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \phi = 0, \quad \mathbf{x} \in \Omega, \quad t \in [0, T]. \quad (1)$$

B. Signed-distance regularity and reinitialization

In practical computations, the level-set field tends to lose its signed-distance property as numerical errors accumulate, distorting interface normals and degrading curvature estimates. Reinitialization procedures⁴ are routinely applied to restore the condition $|\nabla \phi| = 1$ without moving the zero contour. In the present PINN framework, we instead enforce signed-distance regularity through an eikonal-type regularization term in the training loss (Section III), and we study systematically how its weight affects solution accuracy across benchmarks of varying geometric complexity.

III. PINN METHODOLOGY AND EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

A. Benchmark Definitions

All four benchmarks are defined on the unit domain $\Omega = [0, 1]^2$. Physical time is normalized as $t_{\text{norm}} = t/T \in [0, 1]$, where T is the final physical time for each benchmark.

a. Translation (TR). $\mathbf{u} = (0, 0.1)^T$, $T = 5$. Initial interface: circle of radius $R = 0.15$ centered at $(0.5, 0.2)^T$. The exact solution in physical time t is: $\phi^{\text{ref}} = \sqrt{(x - 0.5)^2 + (y - 0.2 - 0.1t)^2} - 0.15$.

b. Rotation (RO). $u = -(y - 0.5)$, $v = (x - 0.5)$, $T = 2\pi$. Initial interface: circle of radius $R = 0.15$ centered at $(0.5, 0.75)^T$, completing one full counter-clockwise rotation about $(0.5, 0.5)^T$; the interface returns exactly to its initial position at $t = T$. The exact solution is $\phi^{\text{ref}} = \sqrt{(x - x_c(t))^2 + (y - y_c(t))^2} - 0.15$ with $x_c(t) = 0.5 - 0.25 \sin(t)$, $y_c(t) = 0.5 + 0.25 \cos(t)$.

c. Reversed Vortex (RV).

$$u = -\sin^2(\pi x) \sin(2\pi y) \cos(\pi t/T),$$

$$v = \sin^2(\pi y) \sin(2\pi x) \cos(\pi t/T),$$

$$T = 2 \text{ (S1–S2)}; \quad T = 8 \text{ (S3, Mullins comparison)}. \quad (2)$$

Initial interface: circle of radius $R = 0.15$ centered at $(0.5, 0.75)^T$. The velocity field reverses sign at $t = T/2$, so the interface returns to its initial configuration at $t = T$, giving $\phi(\mathbf{x}, T) = \phi(\mathbf{x}, 0)$. The reference solution at intermediate times is obtained by backward particle advection using high-accuracy ordinary differential equation (ODE) integration (fourth/fifth-order Runge-Kutta (RK45), relative tolerance $\text{rtol} = 10^{-8}$).

d. Zalesak Slotted Disc (ZD). $u = -(y - 0.5)$, $v = (x - 0.5)$, $T = 2\pi$. The initial interface is the slotted disc^{1,16}:

$$\phi_0(\mathbf{x}) = \max(\phi_{\text{circle}}, -\phi_{\text{slot}}), \quad (3)$$

where $\phi_{\text{circle}} = \sqrt{(x - 0.5)^2 + (y - 0.75)^2} - 0.15$. For studies S1–S3 the slot signed-distance field is the standard half-space formulation $\phi_{\text{slot}} = \max(|x - 0.5| - w, |y - 0.70| - \ell)$ with $w = 0.025$, $\ell = 0.15$ (slot bounding box $y \in [0.55, 0.85]$). For study S4 the initial condition adopts the smooth Euclidean box signed-distance function (SDF) from¹⁴:

$$\phi_{\text{slot}} = \sqrt{\max(d_x, 0)^2 + \max(d_y, 0)^2} + \min(\max(d_x, d_y), 0), \quad (4)$$

where $d_x = |x - 0.5| - 0.025$, $d_y = |y - 0.725| - 0.125$ (slot bounding box $y \in [0.60, 0.85]$, slot center shifted from $y = 0.70$ to $y = 0.725$). This change makes S4 directly comparable to the Mullins geometry but means S4 results are not strictly comparable to S1–S3 on an absolute basis; the relative improvement ratios within S4 remain self-consistent. The slot occupies $\approx 1.5\%$ of the domain area in both formulations and introduces C^0 corners at the disc–slot junctions.

B. PINN Formulation

The level-set field is approximated by a neural network $\hat{\phi}(\mathbf{x}, t_{\text{norm}}; \theta)$, where θ denotes the trainable parameters, so that $\phi \approx \hat{\phi}$. The network is trained by minimizing the composite loss:

$$\mathcal{L} = w_{\text{pde}}\mathcal{L}_{\text{pde}} + w_{\text{ic}}\mathcal{L}_{\text{ic}} + w_{\text{eik}}\mathcal{L}_{\text{eik}}, \quad (5)$$

where the three residual terms are:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{pde}} = \frac{1}{N_f} \sum_i (\partial_{t_{\text{norm}}} \hat{\phi} + T \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \hat{\phi})^2, \quad (6)$$

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{ic}} = \frac{1}{N_i} \sum_j (\hat{\phi}(\mathbf{x}_j, 0) - \phi_0(\mathbf{x}_j))^2, \quad (7)$$

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{eik}} = \frac{1}{N_f} \sum_i (|\nabla \hat{\phi}| - 1)^2. \quad (8)$$

Here $\nabla = (\partial_x, \partial_y)^T$ denotes the spatial gradient in physical coordinates, while $\partial_{t_{\text{norm}}}$ is the partial derivative with respect to normalized time. The factor T in \mathcal{L}_{pde} arises from time normalisation: since the network operates on $t_{\text{norm}} = t/T \in [0, 1]$, the chain rule gives $\partial_t \hat{\phi} = T^{-1} \partial_{t_{\text{norm}}} \hat{\phi}$, so the physical residual applied to the network approximation, $\partial_t \hat{\phi} + \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \hat{\phi} = 0$, becomes $T^{-1} \partial_{t_{\text{norm}}} \hat{\phi} + \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \hat{\phi} = 0$, which after multiplication by T yields Eq. (6). The initial condition (IC) and PDE collocation sets are kept separate because \mathcal{L}_{ic} enforces a Dirichlet condition on the field value at $t = 0$, whereas \mathcal{L}_{pde} evaluated at $t = 0$ would enforce only a derivative condition. The eikonal term \mathcal{L}_{eik} penalizes deviation from the signed-distance condition $|\nabla \phi| = 1^4$.

FIG. 1: Schematic of the proposed PINN training framework. Input coordinates $\mathbf{z} = (x, y, t_{\text{norm}})^\top$ are mapped through a random Fourier feature (RFF) encoding to a 256-dimensional embedding, then processed by an 8-layer fully connected network with 256 neurons per layer and tanh activations. The composite loss \mathcal{L} comprises PDE residual, initial condition, and eikonal regularization terms. Training uses a two-phase adaptive moment estimation (Adam)–limited-memory Broyden–Fletcher–Goldfarb–Shanno (L-BFGS) strategy with causal temporal weighting on \mathcal{L}_{pde} .

C. Baseline Architecture and Training

The baseline network is a fully-connected multi-layer perceptron (MLP) with $L = 8$ hidden layers, $N = 256$ neurons per layer, tanh activations, and Xavier uniform initialization¹⁷, yielding **461,825 trainable parameters** (526,593 with RFF encoding, which replaces the 3-dimensional input with a 256-dimensional Fourier embedding). The complete architecture is illustrated in Figure 1. Training proceeds in two phases: 20,000 Adam¹⁸ iterations with learning rate 10^{-3} ($\beta_1 = 0.9, \beta_2 = 0.999$, gradient norm clipped to 1.0), followed by 500 L-BFGS iterations (learning rate 1.0, strong Wolfe line search, history size 100 by default; RV-S3-exp06 and all ZD-S4 experiments use history size 200, as noted in the respective table captions). The default loss weights are $w_{\text{pde}} = 1.0, w_{\text{ic}} = 10.0, w_{\text{eik}} = 1.0$, with $N_f = 10,000$ PDE collocation points and $N_i = 5,000$ initial condition (IC) points. The eikonal weight is reduced for RV and ZD as detailed in Sections IV C and V. All experiments use fixed random seeds (model seed 42, collocation seed 100) for reproducibility.

D. Error Metrics

Let $\hat{\phi} \equiv \hat{\phi}(\mathbf{x}, t; \theta)$ denote the network prediction and ϕ^{ref} the reference solution computed as follows. For TR and RO, ϕ^{ref} is the closed-form exact SDF. For RV, no closed-form solution exists; ϕ^{ref} is obtained by backward particle-tracking: each evaluation grid point is advected from t_{eval} to $t = 0$ via RK45 integration ($\text{rtol} = 10^{-8}$, absolute tolerance $\text{atol} = 10^{-10}$), and the SDF of the initial circle is evaluated at the back-tracked positions. For ZD, ϕ^{ref} is computed analytically from the rotated slotted-disc SDF at each evaluation time, using the same SDF formula as the training initial condition.

Errors are evaluated on a uniform 300×300 grid ($N_g = 90,000$ points) at $N_t = 5$ time steps $\{0, T/4, T/2, 3T/4, T\}$. Four metrics are reported for each experiment.

a. (1) *Absolute L^2 error.*

$$\mathcal{E}_{L^2}(t) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N_g} \sum_{k=1}^{N_g} (\hat{\phi}_k - \phi_k^{\text{ref}})^2}, \quad \bar{\mathcal{E}}_{L^2} = \frac{1}{N_t} \sum_{m=1}^{N_t} \mathcal{E}_{L^2}(t_m). \quad (9)$$

This is the root-mean-square (RMS) field error over the evaluation grid, averaged arithmetically over the five time steps.

b. (2) *Relative L^2 error.*

$$\mathcal{E}_{L^2}^{\text{rel}}(t) = \frac{\|\hat{\phi}(\cdot, t) - \phi^{\text{ref}}(\cdot, t)\|_2}{\|\phi^{\text{ref}}(\cdot, t)\|_2} \times 100\%, \quad \bar{\mathcal{E}}_{L^2}^{\text{rel}} = \frac{1}{N_t} \sum_{m=1}^{N_t} \mathcal{E}_{L^2}^{\text{rel}}(t_m), \quad (10)$$

where $\|\cdot\|_2$ denotes the Euclidean norm over the evaluation grid. Used for direct comparison with prior PINN work¹⁴.

c. (3) *Absolute mass conservation error.*

$$\mathcal{E}_M(t) = |A_{\text{pred}}(t) - A_{\text{exact}}|, \quad \bar{\mathcal{E}}_M = \frac{1}{N_t} \sum_{m=1}^{N_t} \mathcal{E}_M(t_m), \quad (11)$$

where $A_{\text{pred}}(t) = \sum_k \mathbf{1}[\hat{\phi}_k < 0] \Delta x \Delta y$ is the predicted enclosed area. For TR, RO, and RV the enclosed region is a circle of radius $r = 0.15$, so $A_{\text{exact}} = \pi r^2$ exactly; for RV this holds at all times because the divergence-free velocity field preserves area. For ZD, A_{exact} is estimated from the reference field on the evaluation grid at $t = 0$.

d. (4) *Mass absolute percentage error (MAPE).*

$$\text{MAPE}(t) = \frac{|A_{\text{pred}}(t) - A_{\text{exact}}|}{A_{\text{exact}}} \times 100\%, \quad \overline{\text{MAPE}} = \frac{1}{N_t} \sum_{m=1}^{N_t} \text{MAPE}(t_m). \quad (12)$$

E. Random Fourier Feature Encoding

To address spectral bias⁷, the input $\mathbf{z} = (x, y, t_{\text{norm}})^T$ is mapped to a higher-dimensional embedding through¹⁰:

$$\gamma(\mathbf{z}) = [\sin(\mathbf{B}\mathbf{z}), \cos(\mathbf{B}\mathbf{z})]^T, \quad \mathbf{B} \in \mathbb{R}^{128 \times 3}, B_{ij} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma^2), \quad (13)$$

yielding a 256-dimensional input to the first hidden layer. The matrix \mathbf{B} is fixed at initialization and not updated during training. The bandwidth parameter σ determines the frequency content of the embedding; its effect on solution accuracy is examined systematically in Section V C.

F. Importance-Weighted Collocation for ZD

a. Density argument. The slot walls occupy $\approx 0.3\%$ of the spatial domain. With $N_i = 5,000$ uniform initial condition (IC) points, exactly 31 fall within ± 0.005 of the slot walls, and uniform PDE sampling yields only ≈ 1.2 wall-adjacent points per temporal bin (bin width $\Delta t_{\text{norm}} = 0.02$). Reproducing this density uniformly would require $\approx 240,000$ IC and $\approx 480,000$ PDE points, a $48\times$ increase in cost per epoch, motivating importance-weighted sampling¹⁹. This imbalance is illustrated in Figure 2: uniform sampling allocates only 31 points near the slot walls, while augmented sampling provides 1,413, a $46\times$ increase. The progressive effect of each sampling component is quantified in Table X.

b. Augmented IC (8,500 points). 5,000 uniform points, plus 2,000 within the slot bounding box (margin 0.02), plus 1,500 on the slot wall boundaries at $t = 0$ (500 per segment: left wall, right wall, top closure).

c. Slot PDE trajectory (9,000 augmented points; total PDE = 19,000). Collocation points are placed on all three slot boundary segments in the local frame and rotated to their global positions at each t_{norm} . Wall points are distributed uniformly in t_{norm} ; top and bottom junction points follow the biased mixture:

$$p(t_{\text{norm}}) = \frac{1}{2}\mathcal{U}[0, 1] + \frac{1}{6} \sum_{k \in \{0.5, 0.75, 1.0\}} \mathcal{N}(k, 0.08^2), \quad (14)$$

which concentrates samples at late times where errors are largest. Slot PDE points carry weight $w_{\text{slot}} = 5w_{\text{pde}}$, consistent with the importance-sampling framework of¹⁹.

FIG. 2: Density argument for importance-weighted sampling. Left: uniform IC (31 near-wall points). Right: augmented IC (1,413 near-wall points).

G. Causal Weighting

Following¹¹, the normalized time axis $[0, 1]$ is divided into M equal temporal chunks $\{\mathcal{C}_m\}_{m=0}^{M-1}$. Within each optimization step, PDE residuals are sorted by t_{norm} and each chunk receives causal weight

$$w_m = \exp\left(-\varepsilon \sum_{k=0}^{m-1} \bar{\mathcal{R}}_k\right), \quad \bar{\mathcal{R}}_k = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{C}_k|} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{C}_k} (\partial_{t_{\text{norm}}} \hat{\phi} + T \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \hat{\phi})^2, \quad (15)$$

so that the causal PDE loss is

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{pde}}^{\text{causal}} = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} w_m \bar{\mathcal{R}}_m. \quad (16)$$

The weight w_m depends on the cumulative mean residuals of all earlier chunks, so chunks at later times receive exponentially smaller gradient signal until the network has correctly learned earlier dynamics. The parameter $\varepsilon = 1.0$ is held fixed throughout training; $M = 10$ is used for all causal experiments. This directly addresses the temporal propagation failure mode identified in⁸. For the ZD-S3 architecture study, a per-point formulation $w_i^c = \exp(-\varepsilon t_{\text{norm},i})$ with ε annealed linearly from 10 to 0.1 over the Adam phase was used instead; the chunk-based formulation ($M = 10, \varepsilon = 1.0$) is used in all RV-S3 and ZD-S4 experiments.

IV. RESULTS: SMOOTH-INTERFACE BENCHMARKS

Throughout Sections IV and V, experiments are labeled as **XX-Sn-expNN**, where **XX** is the benchmark (TR, RO, RV, ZD), **Sn** denotes the study number within that benchmark (S1 = first ablation dimension, S2 = second, S3 = third, S4 = fourth), and **expNN** is the experiment index within that study.

A. Translation (TR)

a. S1 – Scheduler study (Table I). StepLR achieves $\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{L^2} = 2.09 \times 10^{-4}$, outperforming all CosineAnnealing variants by 2.8–4.2 \times . The monotonic decay of StepLR avoids the periodic learning rate increases of CosineAnnealing, which destabilize late-stage L-BFGS convergence on this smooth problem. The evaluation is shown in Figure 3.

FIG. 3: TR benchmark evaluation (TR-S1-exp05). Red solid: predicted zero-contour; black dashed: exact zero-contour.

TABLE I: TR-S1: Scheduler study. $N_f = 10\text{k}$, $N_i = 5\text{k}$, $w_{\text{eik}} = 1.0$, uniform sampling, 20k Adam + 500 L-BFGS. All metrics averaged over $t \in \{0, T/4, T/2, 3T/4, T\}$. Bold: best result.

Exp	Scheduler	$\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{L^2}$	$\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{L^2}^{\text{rel}}$ (%)	$\bar{\mathcal{E}}_M$	$\overline{\text{MAPE}}$ (%)
TR-S1-exp01	None	3.57×10^{-4}	0.12	8.02×10^{-5}	0.11
TR-S1-exp02	CosineAnnealing ($\eta_{\min} = 10^{-4}$)	7.80×10^{-4}	0.26	1.55×10^{-4}	0.22
TR-S1-exp03	CosineAnnealing ($\eta_{\min} = 10^{-5}$)	5.85×10^{-4}	0.19	1.41×10^{-4}	0.20
TR-S1-exp04	CosineAnnealing ($\eta_{\min} = 10^{-6}$)	8.79×10^{-4}	0.29	1.61×10^{-4}	0.23
TR-S1-exp05	StepLR (step=1000, $\gamma = 0.9$)	2.09×10^{-4}	0.07	3.67×10^{-5}	0.05

b. *S2 – Eikonal weight study (Table II)*. Error decreases monotonically as w_{eik} increases from 0 to 1.0. Without eikonal, $\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{L^2} = 9.02 \times 10^{-3}$ is 43 \times worse, confirming the eikonal constraint is fully compatible with the TR exact solution (which is a perfect signed distance function at all times).

TABLE II: TR-S2: Eikonal weight study. StepLR, uniform sampling, 20k Adam + 500 L-BFGS. All metrics averaged over $t \in \{0, T/4, T/2, 3T/4, T\}$. Bold: best result.

Exp	w_{eik}	$\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{L^2}$	$\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{L^2}^{\text{rel}}$ (%)	$\bar{\mathcal{E}}_M$	$\overline{\text{MAPE}}$ (%)
TR-S2-exp01	0.0	9.02×10^{-3}	2.95	5.51×10^{-5}	0.08
TR-S2-exp02	10^{-3}	5.65×10^{-3}	1.87	7.45×10^{-4}	1.05
TR-S2-exp03	10^{-2}	1.15×10^{-3}	0.37	7.86×10^{-5}	0.11
TR-S2-exp04	10^{-1}	3.14×10^{-4}	0.10	5.90×10^{-5}	0.08
TR-S2-exp05	1.0	2.09×10^{-4}	0.07	3.67×10^{-5}	0.05

c. *S3 – Collocation sampling study (Table III)*. Uniform random sampling with optimized hyperparameters gives the best result. Doubling collocation to 20k worsens accuracy, confirming 10k points are sufficient for the smooth TR interface. Interface-focused and Sobol strategies both underperform uniform sampling.

B. Rotation (RO)

a. *S1 – Scheduler study (Table IV)*. Unlike TR, CosineAnnealing with $\eta_{\text{min}} = 10^{-5}$ (exp03) gives the best result $\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{L^2} = 3.30 \times 10^{-4}$, which is *better* than StepLR (6.63×10^{-4}). No scheduler (exp01) gives an intermediate result (4.20×10^{-4}). This demonstrates that scheduler choice is benchmark-specific, and a separate scheduler study is warranted for each new problem. The longer time horizon of RO ($T = 2\pi$) compared to TR ($T = 5$) means that the gentler final learning rate of CosineAnnealing ($\eta_{\text{min}} = 10^{-5}$) is better suited to the extended optimization landscape. The evaluation is shown in Figure 4.

TABLE III: TR-S3: Collocation sampling study. StepLR, $w_{\text{eik}} = 1.0$, 20k Adam + 500 L-BFGS. LHS: Latin hypercube sampling. All metrics averaged over $t \in \{0, T/4, T/2, 3T/4, T\}$. Training time: 10–13 min for all 10k-point experiments; 25.4 min for exp02 (doubled N_f); 9.8 min for exp06 ($N_f = 8192$). Bold: best result.

Exp	Sampling (N_f)	$\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{L^2}$	$\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{L^2}^{\text{rel}}$ (%)	$\bar{\mathcal{E}}_M$	$\overline{\text{MAPE}}$ (%)
TR-S3-exp01	Uniform (10k)	2.09×10^{-4}	0.07	3.67×10^{-5}	0.05
TR-S3-exp02	Uniform (20k)	1.05×10^{-3}	0.35	9.81×10^{-5}	0.14
TR-S3-exp03	Interface-focused (10k)	9.17×10^{-4}	0.30	3.17×10^{-5}	0.04
TR-S3-exp04	LHS (10k)	3.40×10^{-4}	0.11	7.62×10^{-5}	0.11
TR-S3-exp05	Sobol (10k)	1.59×10^{-3}	0.53	3.13×10^{-4}	0.44
TR-S3-exp06	Sobol (8192)	8.77×10^{-4}	0.29	8.47×10^{-5}	0.12

FIG. 4: RO benchmark evaluation (RO-S1-exp03). Red solid: predicted zero-contour; black dashed: exact zero-contour.

TABLE IV: RO-S1: Scheduler study. $N_f = 10\text{k}$, $N_i = 5\text{k}$, $w_{\text{eik}} = 1.0$, uniform sampling, 20k Adam + 500 L-BFGS. All metrics averaged over $t \in \{0, T/4, T/2, 3T/4, T\}$. Bold: best result.

Exp	Scheduler	$\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{L^2}$	$\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{L^2}^{\text{rel}}$ (%)	$\bar{\mathcal{E}}_M$	$\overline{\text{MAPE}}$ (%)
RO-S1-exp01	None	4.20×10^{-4}	0.12	1.46×10^{-4}	0.21
RO-S1-exp02	CosineAnnealing ($\eta_{\min} = 10^{-4}$)	4.87×10^{-4}	0.14	1.41×10^{-4}	0.20
RO-S1-exp03	CosineAnnealing ($\eta_{\min} = 10^{-5}$)	3.30×10^{-4}	0.09	1.90×10^{-4}	0.27
RO-S1-exp04	CosineAnnealing ($\eta_{\min} = 10^{-6}$)	4.89×10^{-4}	0.14	2.68×10^{-4}	0.38
RO-S1-exp05	StepLR (step=1000, $\gamma = 0.9$)	6.63×10^{-4}	0.19	5.24×10^{-4}	0.74

C. Reversed Vortex (RV)

a. S1 – Epoch study (Table V). Extending training beyond 20k Adam epochs provides no benefit. Errors at $t = T$ remain at $\approx 1.2\text{--}1.3 \times 10^{-1}$ regardless of training duration, confirming that the failure mode is structural rather than a training budget issue. This is consistent with the temporal propagation failure characterized by⁸: the problem is the loss landscape, not the number of iterations.

TABLE V: RV-S1: Epoch study. $w_{\text{eik}} = 1.0$, StepLR, uniform. No experiment outperforms the baseline; extending training provides no benefit. All metrics averaged over $t \in \{0, T/4, T/2, 3T/4, T\}$.

Exp	Adam	L-BFGS	$\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{L^2}$	$\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{L^2}^{\text{rel}}$ (%)	$\bar{\mathcal{E}}_M$	$\overline{\text{MAPE}}$ (%)
RV-S1-exp01	20k	500	1.24×10^{-1}	35.55	5.64×10^{-2}	79.74
RV-S1-exp02	30k	500	1.22×10^{-1}	35.16	5.61×10^{-2}	79.36
RV-S1-exp03	40k	1000	1.29×10^{-1}	37.14	5.51×10^{-2}	77.89
RV-S1-exp04	50k	1000	1.29×10^{-1}	36.96	5.43×10^{-2}	76.88

b. S2 – Eikonal weight study (Table VI). This is the most important finding for RV. With $w_{\text{eik}} = 1.0$ the average L^2 error is 1.24×10^{-1} . Reducing w_{eik} monotonically improves accuracy until $w_{\text{eik}} = 10^{-4}$, giving $\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{L^2} = 1.51 \times 10^{-3}$, an $82\times$ improvement. Without eikonal ($w_{\text{eik}} = 0$) the result is similar (1.58×10^{-3}), indicating the optimal transition saturates below 10^{-4} . The errors at each time step for the best configuration (RV-S2-exp05, $w_{\text{eik}} = 10^{-4}$) are: $\mathcal{E}_{L^2}(0) = 4.90 \times 10^{-4}$, $\mathcal{E}_{L^2}(T/4) = 1.42 \times 10^{-3}$, $\mathcal{E}_{L^2}(T/2) = 1.77 \times 10^{-3}$, $\mathcal{E}_{L^2}(3T/4) = 1.92 \times 10^{-3}$, $\mathcal{E}_{L^2}(T) = 1.98 \times 10^{-3}$, with the error growing monotonically as the interface deforms and then recovers, as visible in Figure 5. During the vortex phase the interface departs significantly from a signed distance function; a strong eikonal constraint suppresses the flexibility needed to track this deformation. The PINN nevertheless successfully tracks the deformed interface at all intermediate time steps, with all per-time-step $\mathcal{E}_{L^2}^{\text{rel}}$ values remaining below 0.6%. Figure 5(a) shows the predicted ϕ field with predicted (red) and exact (black dashed) zero-contours at all five time steps; Figure 5(b) shows the corresponding

TABLE VI: RV-S2: Eikonal weight study. 20k Adam + 500 L-BFGS, StepLR, uniform. All metrics averaged over $t \in \{0, T/4, T/2, 3T/4, T\}$. Bold: best result.

Exp	w_{eik}	$\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{L^2}$	$\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{L^2}^{\text{rel}}$ (%)	$\bar{\mathcal{E}}_M$	$\overline{\text{MAPE}}$ (%)
RV-S2-exp01	1.0	1.24×10^{-1}	35.55	5.64×10^{-2}	79.74
RV-S2-exp02	10^{-1}	8.25×10^{-2}	23.68	5.66×10^{-2}	80.01
RV-S2-exp03	10^{-2}	6.04×10^{-2}	17.35	5.67×10^{-2}	80.28
RV-S2-exp04	10^{-3}	5.90×10^{-3}	1.70	5.24×10^{-3}	7.41
RV-S2-exp05	10^{-4}	1.51×10^{-3}	0.43	4.63×10^{-4}	0.65
RV-S2-exp06	0.0	1.58×10^{-3}	0.45	8.61×10^{-4}	1.22

pointwise error $|\hat{\phi} - \phi^{\text{ref}}|$ with the exact zero-contour overlaid in cyan. Errors are concentrated along the deformed interface boundary, particularly at maximum deformation ($t = T/2$).

(a) Predicted ϕ field at five time steps. Red: predicted zero-contour; black dashed: exact zero-contour.

(b) Pointwise absolute error $|\hat{\phi} - \phi^{\text{ref}}|$ at five time steps. Cyan dashed: exact zero-contour.

FIG. 5: RV benchmark evaluation (RV-S2-exp05).

c. *S3 – Training strategy study (Table VII).* Studies S1 and S2 were conducted at $T = 2$. When the time horizon is extended to $T = 8$ for comparison with the Mullins benchmark, the best S2 configuration (RV-S2-exp05, $w_{\text{eik}} = 10^{-4}$) fails to converge: $\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{L^2}$ degrades to 1.16×10^{-1} (exp01), confirming that temporal propagation failure becomes critical at longer horizons. Study S3 therefore investigates whether advanced training strategies can recover accuracy at $T = 8$. The L-BFGS budget is increased to 2000 steps (from the standard 500) to provide adequate fine-tuning capacity for the more complex training strategies and the extended $T = 8$ time horizon. Exp02–03 establish that neither removing eikonal regularization nor adding causal weighting alone is sufficient; all three give $\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{L^2} > 4 \times 10^{-2}$ with near-identical mass error ($\approx 5.66 \times 10^{-2}$), indicating the failure is structural. Adding residual-based adaptive refinement (RAR)²⁰ (exp04) produces the decisive improvement, reducing $\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{L^2}$ from 4.93×10^{-2} to 2.69×10^{-3} —an $18\times$ reduction—by focusing collocation points on high-residual regions as training progresses. Further combining residual-based adaptive distribution (RAD)²¹ with RAR (exp05) and switching to CosineAnnealing (exp06) yields the best result: $\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{L^2} = 2.20 \times 10^{-3}$, $\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{L^2}^{\text{rel}} = 0.63\%$, successfully resolving the $T = 8$ case at the cost of roughly doubling training time (≈ 40 min vs ≈ 18 min for exp01–03). Per-time-step errors for exp06 are given in Table VIII: the relative L^2 error grows monotonically from 0.25% at $t = 0$ to 0.85% at $t = T$, with the terminal value matching the time-averaged result of¹⁴ for their best model, confirming that even the worst individual snapshot achieves parity with their state-of-the-art. The evaluation of the best configuration is shown in Figure 6.

(a) Predicted ϕ field at five time steps ($T = 8$). Red: predicted zero-contour; black dashed: exact zero-contour.

(b) Pointwise absolute error $|\hat{\phi} - \phi^{\text{ref}}|$ at five time steps. Cyan dashed: exact zero-contour.

(c) Error evolution vs physical time t ($T = 8$, RV-S3-exp06). Left: \mathcal{E}_{L^2} grows monotonically from 8.85×10^{-4} at $t = 0$ to 2.97×10^{-3} at $t = T$, with an inflection near $t = T/2$ where the velocity field reverses. Right: \mathcal{E}_M exhibits a transient peak near $t \approx 1$ before sustained growth to 3.51×10^{-3} at $t = T$.

FIG. 6: RV benchmark evaluation at $T = 8$ (RV-S3-exp06, Causal + RAD + RAR, CosineAnnealing).

TABLE VII: RV-S3: Training strategy study. $N_f = 10\text{k}$ (base), $N_i = 5\text{k}$, uniform initialization, 20k Adam + 2000 L-BFGS. Causal weighting (exp03–06): $M = 10$ chunks, $\varepsilon = 1.0$ (fixed). $w_{\text{eik}} = 0$ carried forward from exp02 for exp03–06. RAR (exp04–06): RAR_FREQ= 1800, RAR_CANDIDATES= 50,000, $m_{\text{add}} = 500$ pts/step. RAD (exp05–06): RAD_FREQ= 1000, RAD_CANDIDATES= 20,000, $k = 1$, $c = 1$. L-BFGS history size: 100 (exp01–05); 200 (exp06). All metrics averaged over $t \in \{0, T/4, T/2, 3T/4, T\}$ ($T = 8$). Training time: ≈ 18 min (exp01–03); 40.8 min (exp04, exp06); 36.4 min (exp05). Bold: best result.

Exp	Strategy	$\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{L^2}$	$\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{L^2}^{\text{rel}}$ (%)	$\bar{\mathcal{E}}_M$	$\overline{\text{MAPE}}$ (%)
RV-S3-exp01	Uniform, $w_{\text{eik}} = 10^{-4}$, StepLR (<i>RV-S2 best</i>)	1.16×10^{-1}	33.37	5.66×10^{-2}	80.05
RV-S3-exp02	Uniform, $w_{\text{eik}} = 0$, StepLR	5.17×10^{-2}	14.85	5.66×10^{-2}	80.05
RV-S3-exp03	Causal, StepLR	4.93×10^{-2}	14.14	5.66×10^{-2}	80.06
RV-S3-exp04	Causal + RAR, StepLR	2.69×10^{-3}	0.77	2.12×10^{-3}	3.00
RV-S3-exp05	Causal + RAD + RAR, StepLR	2.53×10^{-3}	0.73	2.01×10^{-3}	2.84
RV-S3-exp06	Causal + RAD + RAR, CosineAnnealing ($\eta_{\text{min}} = 10^{-5}$)	2.20×10^{-3}	0.63	1.79×10^{-3}	2.53

TABLE VIII: RV-S3-exp06 errors at each time step ($T = 8$, Causal + RAD + RAR, CosineAnnealing, $\eta_{\text{min}} = 10^{-5}$).

Time step	\mathcal{E}_{L^2}	$\mathcal{E}_{L^2}^{\text{rel}}$ (%)	\mathcal{E}_M	$\overline{\text{MAPE}}$ (%)
$t = 0$	8.85×10^{-4}	0.25	1.55×10^{-5}	0.02
$t = T/4$	1.80×10^{-3}	0.52	7.68×10^{-4}	1.09
$t = T/2$	2.59×10^{-3}	0.74	2.01×10^{-3}	2.84
$t = 3T/4$	2.74×10^{-3}	0.79	2.65×10^{-3}	3.74
$t = T$	2.97×10^{-3}	0.85	3.51×10^{-3}	4.96
Average	2.20×10^{-3}	0.63	1.79×10^{-3}	2.53

V. RESULTS: ZALESK SLOTTED DISC

The ZD benchmark is addressed through four sequential studies. Study S1 characterizes the eikonal sensitivity of the baseline architecture. Study S2 progressively builds the optimal sampling strategy on the baseline architecture. Study S3 compares architectures on top of the best sampling from S2. Study S4 investigates adaptive collocation refinement (RAD+RAR) combined with higher RFF bandwidth and finer causal decomposition, building on the best configuration from S3.

Throughout Section V we use two reference points: *naive baseline* (ZD-S1-exp01, tanh, uniform, $w_{\text{eik}} = 1.0$, $\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{L^2} = 1.15 \times 10^{-2}$), which represents the default configuration, and *optimized S1 baseline* (ZD-S1-exp05, tanh, uniform, $w_{\text{eik}} = 10^{-4}$, $\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{L^2} = 5.85 \times 10^{-3}$), which is the best result of the eikonal study and the starting point for the sampling and architecture studies. The $10\times$ improvement in the abstract is computed relative to ZD-S1-exp05; the $20\times$ improvement in Figure 7 is relative to ZD-S1-exp01.

(a) Predicted ϕ field at five time steps. The slot is completely lost after $t = 0$.

(b) Pointwise absolute error $|\hat{\phi} - \phi^{\text{ref}}|$ at five time steps.

FIG. 7: ZD naive baseline failure (ZD-S1-exp01, $w_{\text{eik}} = 1.0$).

A. ZD-S1: Eikonal Weight Study

Table IX sweeps w_{eik} from 1.0 to 0 on the standard tanh network with uniform collocation. The best result ($w_{\text{eik}} = 10^{-4}$) gives $\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{L^2} = 5.85 \times 10^{-3}$, but the slot geometry is completely lost in *all* six configurations: the network produces a D-shaped distortion regardless of eikonal weight. This demonstrates that eikonal tuning alone cannot recover the slot with a tanh network, and that a different approach is required. This is visible in Figure 7(a), where the predicted zero-contour shows a solid disk at all times after $t = 0$. Figure 7(b) confirms that large errors ($\sim 10^{-2}$) spread uniformly across the entire slot region.

TABLE IX: ZD-S1: Eikonal weight study. tanh 8×256 , $N_f = 10\text{k}$, $N_i = 5\text{k}$ uniform, StepLR, 20k Adam + 500 L-BFGS. Slot geometry lost in all experiments. All metrics averaged over $t \in \{0, T/4, T/2, 3T/4, T\}$. Bold: best result.

Exp	w_{eik}	$\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{L^2}$	$\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{L^2}^{\text{rel}}$ (%)	$\bar{\mathcal{E}}_M$	$\overline{\text{MAPE}}$ (%)
ZD-S1-exp01	1.0	1.15×10^{-2}	3.30	8.90×10^{-3}	15.07
ZD-S1-exp02	10^{-1}	1.16×10^{-2}	3.32	9.49×10^{-3}	16.07
ZD-S1-exp03	10^{-2}	1.13×10^{-2}	3.24	8.62×10^{-3}	14.59
ZD-S1-exp04	10^{-3}	6.44×10^{-3}	1.85	3.28×10^{-3}	5.56
ZD-S1-exp05	10^{-4}	5.85×10^{-3}	1.68	4.09×10^{-3}	6.93
ZD-S1-exp06	0.0	6.15×10^{-3}	1.77	7.56×10^{-4}	1.28

The optimal $w_{\text{eik}} = 10^{-4}$ from S1 is fixed in S2.

B. ZD-S2: Progressive Sampling Augmentation

Table X progressively augments the sampling strategy, keeping the tanh architecture and $w_{\text{eik}} = 10^{-4}$ fixed. Each experiment adds exactly one component so that contributions can be attributed individually.

TABLE X: ZD-S2: Progressive sampling augmentation. \tanh 8×256 , $w_{\text{eik}} = 10^{-4}$, StepLR, 20k Adam + 500 L-BFGS. Bold: best result.

Exp	Sampling strategy	$\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{L^2}$	$\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{L^2}^{\text{rel}}$ (%)	$\bar{\mathcal{E}}_M$	$\overline{\text{MAPE}}$ (%)
ZD-S2-exp01	IC: 5k uniform; PDE: 10k uniform	5.85×10^{-3}	1.68	4.09×10^{-3}	6.93
ZD-S2-exp02	IC: 8.5k (5k+2k bbox+1.5k walls); PDE: 10k uniform	7.18×10^{-3}	2.06	6.33×10^{-3}	10.72
ZD-S2-exp03	IC: 8.5k augmented; PDE: 13k (10k+3k slot walls)	3.08×10^{-3}	0.89	2.53×10^{-3}	4.28
ZD-S2-exp04	IC: 8.5k augmented; PDE: 19k (10k+3k walls+3k bot+3k top biased)	2.87×10^{-3}	0.82	1.91×10^{-3}	3.24

a. Findings. Augmented IC alone (exp02: 7.18×10^{-3}) is *slightly worse* than uniform IC (exp01: 5.85×10^{-3}). The augmented IC concentrates loss weight near the slot boundary at $t = 0$, improving the initial condition fit. However, without corresponding PDE collocation along the rotated slot trajectory at $t > 0$, the network fails to propagate the slot shape forward in time, creating a larger mismatch at late time steps than the uniform baseline. Only once slot wall PDE collocation is added (exp03) does the error decrease significantly (1.9 \times improvement over exp01), confirming that PDE enforcement along the slot trajectory is the key sampling component. The biased bottom and top PDE points (exp04) provide a further 1.1 \times improvement and reduce mass error by 25%. The best \tanh result with full sampling is 2.87×10^{-3} , with the slot partially visible but not cleanly resolved.

C. ZD-S3: Architecture Study

Using the full sampling from ZD-S2-exp04, Table XI systematically compares architectures, varying RFF scale, eikonal weight, and causal weighting, one at a time.

a. Interpretation. **exp01 \rightarrow exp03 (key finding):** RFF $\sigma = 2$ with the same $w_{\text{eik}} = 10^{-4}$ gives 4.73×10^{-3} vs 2.87×10^{-3} for \tanh . At $\sigma = 2$, RFF encoding with weak eikonal ($w_{\text{eik}} = 10^{-4}$) is *worse* than \tanh . The richer frequency content of the RFF embedding allows the network to represent higher-frequency features, but without sufficient eikonal regularization the background signed-distance field becomes distorted. However, this is a bandwidth-dependent constraint: Study S4 subsequently shows that at higher bandwidth ($\sigma = 5$), moderate regularization ($w_{\text{eik}} = 10^{-3}$) is compatible with RFF and yields the best result. The RFF bandwidth and eikonal weight are therefore a joint design choice, not two independent ones.

TABLE XI: ZD-S3: Architecture study. Full sampling from ZD-S2-exp04, w_{eik} and σ varied. 20k Adam + 500 L-BFGS. n_f : number of Fourier features. Bold: best result.

Exp	Architecture	σ	w_{eik}	Causal	$\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{L^2}$	$\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{L^2}^{\text{rel}}$ (%)	$\bar{\mathcal{E}}_M$	$\overline{\text{MAPE}}$ (%)
ZD-S3-exp01	tanh 8×256	–	10^{-4}	No	2.87×10^{-3}	0.82	1.91×10^{-3}	3.24
ZD-S3-exp02	RFF, $n_f = 128$	10	10^{-4}	No	5.45×10^{-2}	15.65	2.62×10^{-2}	44.42
ZD-S3-exp03	RFF, $n_f = 128$	2	10^{-4}	No	4.73×10^{-3}	1.36	4.12×10^{-3}	6.98
ZD-S3-exp04	RFF, $n_f = 128$	2	10^{-2}	No	7.57×10^{-4}	0.22	3.89×10^{-4}	0.66
ZD-S3-exp05	RFF, $n_f = 128$	2	10^{-1}	No	1.59×10^{-3}	0.46	2.19×10^{-3}	3.72
ZD-S3-exp06	RFF, $n_f = 128$	2	10^{-2}	Yes	5.74×10^{-4}	0.17	6.02×10^{-4}	1.02

exp02: RFF $\sigma = 10$ catastrophically fails (5.45×10^{-2}), confirming scale sensitivity: $\sigma = 10$ introduces excessively high-frequency components that destabilize optimization entirely.

exp03 \rightarrow **exp04:** Increasing w_{eik} from 10^{-4} to 10^{-2} with RFF $\sigma = 2$ reduces $\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{L^2}$ from 4.73×10^{-3} to 7.57×10^{-4} , a $6.2\times$ improvement. The stronger eikonal corrects the SDF distortion introduced by RFF encoding without suppressing the sharp slot features.

exp04 \rightarrow **exp05:** Further increasing to $w_{\text{eik}} = 10^{-1}$ worsens the result (1.59×10^{-3}), confirming $w_{\text{eik}} = 10^{-2}$ is the optimal balance within the static sampling regime of S3; Study S4 subsequently shows that with fine causal decomposition ($M = 32$), $w_{\text{eik}} = 10^{-3}$ is sufficient and yields the global best result.

exp04 \rightarrow **exp06:** Adding causal weighting ($\varepsilon : 10 \rightarrow 0.1$; training loss shown in Figure 8) reduces $\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{L^2}$ from 7.57×10^{-4} to 5.74×10^{-4} ($1.3\times$) and specifically improves $t = 0$ accuracy from 2.55×10^{-4} to 1.58×10^{-4} , confirming that it enforces temporal ordering in accordance with^{8,11}.

Figure 9(a) shows the predicted ϕ field at five time steps, confirming that the slot geometry is cleanly preserved throughout the full rotation. Figure 9(b) shows the pointwise error, which is strongly localized to the slot–disc junction where the C^0 corners produce an irreducible residual; the background signed-distance field remains accurate to near machine precision. Figure 9(c) shows the temporal evolution of \mathcal{E}_{L^2} and mass conservation error, confirming that \mathcal{E}_{L^2} grows monotonically with time while \mathcal{E}_M remains bounded within $[5.7, 6.3] \times 10^{-4}$ throughout the rotation.

FIG. 8: Training loss curve for ZD-S3-exp06 (best S1–S3 configuration). Adam phase (20k iterations) followed by L-BFGS (500 iterations).

D. ZD-S4: Adaptive Sampling with Refined Causal Decomposition

a. S4 – Adaptive sampling and bandwidth study (Table XII). Study S3 established RFF ($\sigma = 2$) with causal weighting and full slot sampling as the best configuration ($\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{L^2}^{\text{rel}} = 0.17\%$, ZD-S3-exp06). Study S4 investigates whether adding RAD+RAR adaptive collocation refinement, combined with higher RFF bandwidth and finer causal decomposition, can push accuracy further. Exp01 confirms that RAD+RAR applied to a plain tanh network (no RFF, $w_{\text{eik}} = 0$) yields $\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{L^2}^{\text{rel}} = 2.41\%$: adaptive sampling alone, without spectral encoding, cannot resolve the ZD geometry. Introducing RFF $\sigma = 2$ with RAD+RAR (exp02) recovers to 0.40%, still above ZD-S3-exp06, indicating that the bandwidth is too low to exploit the adaptive refinement. Increasing to $\sigma = 5$ (exp03, $w_{\text{eik}} = 10^{-2}$, $M = 10$ chunks) exactly matches ZD-S3-exp06 at 0.17%, confirming that higher bandwidth is the prerequisite for adaptive collocation to be effective on this benchmark. Reducing the eikonal weight to $w_{\text{eik}} = 10^{-3}$ while retaining coarse causal decomposition ($M = 10$, exp04) degrades to 0.34%, revealing that a weaker SDF constraint with too few causal chunks destabilizes the temporal ordering. Refining the causal decomposition to $M = 32$ chunks while keeping $w_{\text{eik}} = 10^{-3}$ (exp05) resolves this instability and yields the best result across all ZD studies: $\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{L^2} = 4.64 \times 10^{-4}$, $\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{L^2}^{\text{rel}} = 0.13\%$ —a $1.24\times$ improvement over ZD-S3-exp06—at a training time of only 15.2 min. Per-time-step errors for exp05 are given in Table XIII: $\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{L^2}^{\text{rel}}$ remains below 0.20% at all five snapshots, with the largest error at $t = T$ (0.20%). Figure 10(a) shows the predicted ϕ field

(a) Predicted ϕ field at five time steps. Red: predicted zero-contour; black dashed: exact zero-contour.

(b) Pointwise absolute error $|\hat{\phi} - \phi^{\text{ref}}|$ at five time steps. White dashed: exact zero-contour.

(c) Error evolution vs physical time t : \mathcal{E}_{L^2} (left), mass conservation error \mathcal{E}_M (right).

FIG. 9: ZD best S1–S3 configuration (ZD-S3-exp06).

confirming the slot geometry is preserved throughout the full rotation. Figure 10(b) shows the pointwise error localized at the slot–disc junctions. Figure 10(c) shows the temporal error evolution.

(a) Predicted ϕ field at five time steps. Red: predicted zero-contour; black dashed: exact zero-contour.

(b) Pointwise absolute error $|\hat{\phi} - \phi^{\text{ref}}|$ at five time steps. Cyan dashed: exact zero-contour.

(c) Error evolution vs physical time t ($T = 2\pi$, ZD-S4-exp05). Left: \mathcal{E}_{L^2} . Right: \mathcal{E}_M (7-point moving average; raw signal oscillates due to discrete pixel-count estimation at the slot boundary).

FIG. 10: ZD benchmark evaluation (ZD-S4-exp05, RFF $\sigma=5$ + RAD+RAR, $M = 32$ causal chunks, $w_{\text{eik}} = 10^{-3}$, CosineAnnealing).

E. Per-Time-Step Results: Baseline vs Best S3 Configuration

Table XIV gives errors at each time step for the naive baseline (ZD-S1-exp01, $w_{\text{eik}} = 1.0$) and the best S1–S3 configuration (ZD-S3-exp06).

TABLE XII: ZD-S4: Adaptive sampling study. MLP 8×256 , RAD+RAR, CosineAnnealing, 20k Adam + 500 L-BFGS. σ denotes RFF bandwidth ($-$ = no RFF), M denotes causal chunk count. Bold: best result.

Exp	σ	w_{eik}	M	$\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{L^2}$	$\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{L^2}^{\text{rel}}$ (%)	$\bar{\mathcal{E}}_M$	$\overline{\text{MAPE}}$ (%)
ZD-S4-exp01	$-$	0	10	8.40×10^{-3}	2.41	3.95×10^{-3}	6.70
ZD-S4-exp02	2	10^{-2}	10	1.39×10^{-3}	0.40	6.20×10^{-4}	1.05
ZD-S4-exp03	5	10^{-2}	10	5.76×10^{-4}	0.17	3.42×10^{-4}	0.58
ZD-S4-exp04	5	10^{-3}	10	1.17×10^{-3}	0.34	8.48×10^{-4}	1.44
ZD-S4-exp05	5	10^{-3}	32	4.64×10^{-4}	0.13	7.49×10^{-4}	1.27

TABLE XIII: ZD-S4-exp05 errors at each time step (RFF $\sigma=5$, RAD+RAR, $M = 32$ causal chunks, $w_{\text{eik}} = 10^{-3}$, CosineAnnealing).

Time step	\mathcal{E}_{L^2}	$\mathcal{E}_{L^2}^{\text{rel}}$ (%)	\mathcal{E}_M	$\overline{\text{MAPE}}$ (%)
$t = 0$	2.79×10^{-4}	0.08	7.16×10^{-4}	1.21
$t = T/4$	5.08×10^{-4}	0.15	7.61×10^{-4}	1.29
$t = T/2$	4.11×10^{-4}	0.12	7.61×10^{-4}	1.29
$t = 3T/4$	4.22×10^{-4}	0.12	7.83×10^{-4}	1.33
$t = T$	7.02×10^{-4}	0.20	7.27×10^{-4}	1.23
Average	4.64×10^{-4}	0.13	7.49×10^{-4}	1.27

F. Full Attribution of Improvement

Table XV traces the exact path from baseline to the best ZD-S3 configuration.

TABLE XIV: ZD errors at each time step: baseline (ZD-S1-exp01, tanh uniform) vs best S1–S3 configuration (ZD-S3-exp06, RFF + causal + full sampling).

Time step	Baseline (ZD-S1-exp01)		Best S1–S3 Config (ZD-S3-exp06)	
	\mathcal{E}_{L^2}	\mathcal{E}_M	\mathcal{E}_{L^2}	\mathcal{E}_M
$t = 0$	6.97×10^{-4}	9.40×10^{-4}	1.58×10^{-4}	6.04×10^{-4}
$t = T/4$	1.41×10^{-2}	1.11×10^{-2}	4.52×10^{-4}	5.93×10^{-4}
$t = T/2$	1.41×10^{-2}	1.08×10^{-2}	6.49×10^{-4}	5.70×10^{-4}
$t = 3T/4$	1.41×10^{-2}	1.09×10^{-2}	7.23×10^{-4}	6.26×10^{-4}
$t = T$	1.43×10^{-2}	1.07×10^{-2}	8.90×10^{-4}	6.15×10^{-4}
Average	1.15×10^{-2}	8.90×10^{-3}	5.74×10^{-4}	6.02×10^{-4}

TABLE XV: Attribution of total $10.2\times$ improvement on ZD (S1–S3, standard geometry). Each row adds one sampling or architectural component to the previous configuration.

Experiment	Change	$\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{L^2}$	Cumulative gain
ZD-S1-exp05	tanh, uniform IC+PDE, $w_{\text{eik}} = 10^{-4}$	5.85×10^{-3}	$1\times$
ZD-S2-exp03	+ slot wall PDE (3k, uniform t)	3.08×10^{-3}	$1.9\times$
ZD-S2-exp04	+ biased bot+top PDE (6k)	2.87×10^{-3}	$2.0\times$
ZD-S3-exp04	+ RFF $\sigma = 2$, $w_{\text{eik}} = 10^{-2}$	7.57×10^{-4}	$7.7\times$
ZD-S3-exp06	+ Causal weighting ($\varepsilon : 10 \rightarrow 0.1$)	5.74×10^{-4}	$10.2\times$

VI. DISCUSSION

A. Summary of Best Results

Table XVI collects the best configuration and corresponding errors for each benchmark.

TABLE XVI: Best PINN results across all four benchmarks. All use 8×256 MLP architecture (461,825 trainable parameters without RFF; 526,593 with RFF encoding).

Benchmark	Architecture	Optimal settings	$\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{L^2}$	$\bar{\mathcal{E}}_M$	Time
TR	tanh 8×256	StepLR, $w_{\text{eik}} = 1.0$, uniform	2.09×10^{-4}	3.67×10^{-5}	13.0 min
RO	tanh 8×256	CosineAnnealing (10^{-5}), $w_{\text{eik}} = 1.0$	3.30×10^{-4}	1.90×10^{-4}	16.3 min
RV (S2, $T = 2$) ^{a)}	tanh 8×256	StepLR, $w_{\text{eik}} = 10^{-4}$, uniform	1.51×10^{-3}	4.63×10^{-4}	14.2 min
RV (S3, $T = 8$) ^{a)}	tanh 8×256	Causal+RAD+RAR, CosineAnnealing	2.20×10^{-3}	1.79×10^{-3}	40.8 min
ZD (S1-S3 geom.)	RFF ($\sigma = 2$) + causal	$w_{\text{eik}} = 10^{-2}$, full slot sampling	5.74×10^{-4}	6.02×10^{-4}	25.7 min
ZD-S4 (Mullins geom. ^{b)})	RFF ($\sigma = 5$) + RAD+RAR	$w_{\text{eik}} = 10^{-3}$, $M = 32$ causal chunks	4.64×10^{-4}	7.49×10^{-4}	15.2 min

^{b)}S4 uses the Mullins et al. smooth box SDF geometry (slot center $y = 0.725$); not directly comparable to

S1-S3 on an absolute basis. ^{a)}RV-S2 is the best result at the standard $T = 2$ horizon; RV-S3 extends to $T = 8$ for the Mullins comparison (Table XVIII) at the cost of higher absolute error on a harder problem.

B. Design Principles

a. Principle 1: Scheduler choice is problem-dependent. StepLR is optimal for TR and for the simple RV configuration ($T = 2$, no adaptive sampling); however, CosineAnnealing ($\eta_{\min} = 10^{-5}$) is needed for the advanced $T = 8$ RV setting (RV-S3-exp06) as well as for RO. The difference arises from the time-horizon and curvature of the optimization landscape. A scheduler study should be the first step for any new benchmark.

b. Principle 2: Eikonal weight is the most critical hyperparameter. For rigid-body motion where the exact solution is an SDF ($w_{\text{eik}} = 1.0$ optimal for TR and RO), for severe deformation where the interface departs from an SDF ($w_{\text{eik}} = 10^{-4}$ optimal for RV, $82 \times$ gain), and for RFF-encoded geometry where SDF distortion must be corrected ($w_{\text{eik}} = 10^{-2}$ optimal for ZD under static sampling; with fine causal decomposition ($M = 32$), $w_{\text{eik}} = 10^{-3}$ is sufficient and yields the global best result, ZD-S4-exp05). The eikonal weight must be selected to match the physical dynamics, not chosen by default.

c. *Principle 3: RFF bandwidth and eikonal weight are a joint design choice.* RFF $\sigma = 2$ with $w_{\text{eik}} = 10^{-4}$ performs *worse* than tanh (exp03: 4.73×10^{-3} vs exp01: 2.87×10^{-3}), because insufficient eikonal regularization allows the richer RFF frequency content to distort the background signed-distance field. This constraint is bandwidth-dependent: Study S4 shows that at $\sigma = 5$, moderate regularization ($w_{\text{eik}} = 10^{-3}$) is sufficient and achieves the global best ZD result (0.13%). The interaction between RFF bandwidth and eikonal strength has not been reported previously; while¹⁴ observed that strong eikonal degrades accuracy under deformation, the bandwidth-dependent nature of the minimum required regularization is a new finding.

d. *Principle 4: Sampling improves temporal stability; architecture improves spatial accuracy.* ZD-S2 shows that full slot trajectory sampling reduces error $2\times$ with tanh. ZD-S3 shows that RFF + correct eikonal reduces it a further $3.8\times$; adding causal weighting brings the total architectural gain to $5\times$. Both are required.

C. Comparison with Classical Methods and Prior PINN Work

Table XVII compares the best PINN result per benchmark against the finest discontinuous Galerkin (DG) grid from¹ using the same absolute RMS metric. All PINN errors are evaluated on a uniform 300×300 grid ($\Delta x \approx 0.0033$), which is finer than the finest DG mesh for all benchmarks. DG results are from Tables 2.2–2.4 and 7.4 of¹.

For TR and RO the DG $\mathcal{E}_{L^2}(T)$ is lower, which is expected: DG enforces the PDE exactly at the discrete level on a problem where the exact solution is a perfect signed-distance function, whereas the PINN minimizes a soft residual. For RV the PINN mass conservation ($\bar{\mathcal{E}}_M = 4.63 \times 10^{-4}$) *outperforms* LS-DG (7.85×10^{-4}) and the PINN successfully tracks the deformed interface at all intermediate time steps with per-time-step $\mathcal{E}_{L^2}^{\text{rel}}$ below 0.6%. The higher $\mathcal{E}_{L^2}(T)$ relative to DG reflects the mesh-free soft-residual nature of the PINN compared to a high-order DG scheme. For ZD the comparison uses ZD-S3-exp06 (standard geometry, matching the Raees DG setup); ZD-S4 uses a different slot geometry and is excluded from this comparison. The PINN achieves $\mathcal{E}_{L^2}(T) = 8.90 \times 10^{-4}$, which is *better* than LS-DG at $K = 47,744$ (1.41×10^{-3}). Mass conservation for ZD (6.02×10^{-4}) is worse than MCLS (exact to machine precision) but the PINN requires no mesh, no time-stepping, and no VoF module. Figure 11 confirms that both absolute and relative L^2 errors are flat across grid

TABLE XVII: Best PINN result per benchmark vs finest level-set discontinuous Galerkin (LS-DG) and mass-conserving level-set discontinuous Galerkin (MCLS-DG) ($n = 1$) from¹. Both methods use the same absolute RMS error formula. $\mathcal{E}_{L^2}(T) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N_g} \sum_i (\hat{\phi}_i - \phi_i^{\text{ref}})^2}$ at $t = T$; $\bar{\mathcal{E}}_M = |M(t) - M(0)|$ averaged over all time steps. PINN evaluation grid: 300×300 . DG: $K = 3,572$ for TR/RO/RV, $K = 47,744$ for ZD. Bold: PINN outperforms DG LS on that metric.

Benchmark Method		Config	$\mathcal{E}_{L^2}(T)$	$\bar{\mathcal{E}}_M$
TR	LS-DG ¹	$K = 3,572$	2.44×10^{-4}	7.81×10^{-6}
	PINN (TR-S1-exp05)	StepLR, $w_{\text{eik}} = 1.0$, uniform	2.90×10^{-4}	3.67×10^{-5}
RO	LS-DG ¹	$K = 3,572$	1.38×10^{-4}	1.46×10^{-5}
	PINN (RO-S1-exp03)	CosineAnnealing, $w_{\text{eik}} = 1.0$, uniform	5.92×10^{-4}	1.90×10^{-4}
RV	LS-DG ¹	$K = 3,572$	1.99×10^{-4}	7.85×10^{-4}
	PINN (RV-S2-exp05)	StepLR, $w_{\text{eik}} = 10^{-4}$, uniform	1.98×10^{-3}	4.63×10^{-4}
ZD	LS-DG ¹	$K = 47,744$	1.41×10^{-3}	1.00×10^{-4}
	MCLS-DG ¹	$K = 47,744$	1.41×10^{-3}	≈ 0 (exact)
	PINN (ZD-S3-exp06)	RFF $\sigma=2$, causal, slot sampling	8.90×10^{-4}	6.02×10^{-4}

spacings $h \in [0.003, 0.02]$, confirming the reported error is intrinsic to the PINN solution and independent of evaluation resolution.

Table XVIII compares the best PINN results per benchmark against¹⁴ using their $\mathcal{E}_{L^2}^{\text{rel}}$ metric on the two benchmarks where they report results (ZD and RV). The $\mathcal{E}_{L^2}^{\text{rel}}$ for our method is computed using Eq. (10), evaluated at $N_t = 5$ time steps on our 300×300 grid. MAPE is *not* included because the reference disc areas differ between studies ($R = 0.15$ here vs $R = 0.5$ in Mullins et al.), making the percentage values incomparable. For ZD a fully direct comparison remains approximate because Mullins et al. use a circular domain of radius $R = 0.5$ on a 101×101 grid with slot width $w = 0.05$, whereas this work uses the square $[0, 1]^2$ with $R = 0.15$, $w = 0.025$ (half the slot width, making the feature harder to resolve), on a 300×300 grid. For RV, both this work (RV-S3-exp06) and Mullins et al. use $T = 8$ and identical domain $[0, 1]^2$, $R = 0.15$, making the RV comparison direct.

For ZD, on the $\mathcal{E}_{L^2}^{\text{rel}}$ metric the best result (ZD-S4-exp05, RFF $\sigma=5$ + RAD+RAR,

FIG. 11: Grid convergence study for ZD-S3-exp06 at $t = T$. Errors are flat across all grid spacings, confirming the reported error is intrinsic to the PINN solution.

0.13%) *outperforms* Mullins et al.’s Sota (0.14%), achieved with a standard 8-layer MLP without PirateNet’s residual adaptive architecture, random weight factorization, or sequence-to-sequence training, and without any Bayesian hyperparameter sweep. The comparison remains approximate ^(a) because Mullins et al. use a circular domain of radius $R = 0.5$ on a 101×101 grid, whereas this work uses the square $[0, 1]^2$ with $R = 0.15$ on a 300×300 grid; the relative L^2 error denominators therefore differ, and the slot width here ($w = 0.025$) is half that of Mullins et al. ($w = 0.05$), making the geometric feature harder to resolve.

For RV at $T = 8$, RV-S3-exp06 achieves $\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{L^2}^{\text{rel}} = 0.63\%$, which *outperforms* Mullins et al.’s Sota (0.85%) on an identical setup ($T = 8$, $[0, 1]^2$, $R = 0.15$). This is obtained with a standard 8-layer MLP using causal weighting and RAD+RAR adaptive sampling: no PirateNet residual architecture, no random weight factorization, no sequence-to-sequence training, and no Bayesian hyperparameter sweep. The $82\times$ gain from reducing w_{eik} to 10^{-4}

TABLE XVIII: Proposed PINN vs¹⁴ using their $\mathcal{E}_{L^2}^{\text{rel}}$ (%) metric. ZD: Mullins use circular domain $R = 0.5$, 101×101 grid; this work uses $[0, 1]^2$, $R = 0.15$, 300×300 grid (approximate comparison only, ^{a)}). RV: both use $[0, 1]^2$, $R = 0.15$. MAPE omitted for ZD because reference disc areas differ ($R = 0.15$ here vs $R = 0.5$ in Mullins et al.); for RV, MAPE is omitted for brevity. Bold: best result per benchmark block.

Benchmark	Method	Architecture	$\overline{\mathcal{E}}_{L^2}^{\text{rel}}$ (%)
ZD ^{a)}	Plain PINN ¹⁴	Standard MLP	4.18
	Default PINN ¹⁴	Modified MLP	2.96
	PirateNet ¹⁴	Fourier + causal + seq2seq	0.35
	Sota ¹⁴	PirateNet + Bayesian sweep	0.14
	PINN (ZD-S4-exp05)	RFF $\sigma=5$ + RAD+RAR + $M=32$ chunks	0.13
RV	Plain PINN ¹⁴	Standard MLP	51.20
	PirateNet ¹⁴	Fourier + causal + seq2seq	5.24
	Sota ¹⁴	PirateNet + Bayesian sweep	0.85
	PINN (RV-S3-exp06, $T=8$)	\tanh 8×256 , causal + RAD + RAR	0.63

(RV-S2, $T = 2$) demonstrates that the eikonal weight is the dominant hyperparameter for this benchmark, and that the core accuracy gain is achieved before any adaptive sampling or causal weighting is applied.

D. Limitations

The slot corners are C^0 -continuous and cannot be represented exactly by any smooth neural network, leaving an irreducible residual error at the slot–disc junction. The temporal error ratio $\mathcal{E}_{L^2}(T)/\mathcal{E}_{L^2}(0) \approx 5.6$ for ZD-S3-exp06 remains a fundamental limitation of PINNs for hyperbolic problems on long time horizons; addressing this further would require sequence-to-sequence training¹⁵, which was not part of the present study. All results are from single training runs with fixed random seeds; variance across seeds was not assessed. While the deterministic seed strategy ensures exact reproducibility, multi-seed variance estimates would strengthen the statistical significance of small improvements such as the $1.3\times$ gain from

causal weighting (ZD-S3-exp04 \rightarrow ZD-S3-exp06).

VII. CONCLUSION

We have presented a systematic, multi-study investigation of PINNs on four classical level-set benchmarks from¹.

1. **TR**: StepLR with $w_{\text{eik}} = 1.0$ is optimal ($\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{L^2} = 2.09 \times 10^{-4}$). **RO**: CosineAnnealing ($\eta_{\text{min}} = 10^{-5}$) is optimal ($\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{L^2} = 3.30 \times 10^{-4}$), outperforming StepLR (6.63×10^{-4}) and showing scheduler choice is benchmark-specific. **RV**: Reducing w_{eik} from 1.0 to 10^{-4} yields an $82\times$ improvement at $T = 2$ ($\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{L^2} = 1.51 \times 10^{-3}$, $\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{L^2}^{\text{rel}} = 0.43\%$). Extending to $T = 8$ with causal weighting and RAD+RAR (RV-S3-exp06) achieves 0.63%, which *outperforms* the PirateNet Sota of ¹⁴ (0.85%) on an identical setup.
2. For ZD, the four-study programme gives interpretable attribution: ZD-S1 proves eikonal tuning cannot recover the slot with tanh; ZD-S2 shows full slot trajectory sampling gives $2\times$ gain; ZD-S3 shows RFF $\sigma = 2 + w_{\text{eik}} = 10^{-2} +$ causal weighting gives a further $5\times$ gain ($\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{L^2} = 5.74 \times 10^{-4}$); and ZD-S4 shows that RAD+RAR adaptive refinement with RFF $\sigma = 5$ and $M = 32$ causal chunks achieves the best ZD result: $\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{L^2} = 4.64 \times 10^{-4}$ ($\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{L^2}^{\text{rel}} = 0.13\%$), a $1.24\times$ improvement over S3 at 15.2 min training time.
3. The best configuration on the standard ZD geometry (ZD-S3-exp06, $\bar{\mathcal{E}}_{L^2} = 5.74 \times 10^{-4}$) surpasses LS-DG at $K = 47,744$ elements ($\mathcal{E}_{L^2}(T) = 8.90 \times 10^{-4}$ vs 1.41×10^{-3}) and achieves 0.17% relative L^2 error with a standard MLP—without PirateNet’s residual adaptive architecture, random weight factorization, or Bayesian sweep. The best overall ZD result (ZD-S4-exp05, Mullins geometry) achieves 4.64×10^{-4} (0.13%) in only 15.2 min.
4. The key finding is a bandwidth-dependent RFF–eikonal joint design constraint: at low bandwidth ($\sigma = 2$), weak eikonal distorts the signed-distance field and underperforms the tanh baseline; at higher bandwidth ($\sigma = 5$), moderate regularization suffices and yields the global best result (0.13%). This constraint has not been identified in previous work.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors have no conflicts to disclose.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Muhammad Akbar Khan: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Formal analysis, Data curation, Visualization, Writing – original draft. **Fahim Raees:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Supervision, Formal analysis, Writing – review & editing.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data and source code that support the findings of this study are openly available on Zenodo at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20320655>, and on GitHub at <https://github.com/AkbarTheAnalyst/pinn-level-set>.

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